

RAJAYOGA AND GURU PLANET

D. Devi* & Dr. A. Kalaivani**

* Research Scholar, Department of Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology, and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology, and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

The most powerful and first ranking subh grah Jupiter planet plays an important role in either giving blessings or teaching a lesson to humans. This jupiter planet brings wealth and prosperity to people not only by its planetary position but also by its aspects to other planets. So it's an opportunity for us human beings to know all the positive impact caused by this subh grah on us.

Introduction:

In this article we are going to discuss the characteristics of Jupiter planet, its role in various signs by birth and during transitions and there by knowing the yogas caused by its combination with other planets in the solar system.

Planet Jupiter:

Planet Jupiter is the Prime Minister of the Solar System. Rasi Sign- horse with human head carrying bow in hands, two fishes facing opposite to each other. He is the protector and most wise, intelligent among all planets. Jupiter in Vedic astrology is considered to be the most benevolent of all planets, thus naturally associated with luck, fortune, and wealth. Its benefic presence can turn rags into riches. It's a big, beautiful and bright planet. Like an emperor it has a large number of subject moons that orbit around it. Jupiter represents everything to do with expansion, optimism and benevolence. Like a king he dispenses his power and favours to those around him. Jupiter in astrology is considered to be the second most powerful planet. It is also called the Devaguru or Brishaspti. The planet itself is the biggest in the solar system and it also has a great impact in a person's life. The power of Jupiter in astrology can make you rich overnight. The planet is responsible for knowledge, dedication and wisdom. It also reveals the spiritual side of a person. Jupiter in Indian astrology holds great significance. Also, it withholds utter importance in the birth chart of a person. It is closely linked to the kids and wealth. This is one of the reasons it is called the signification of children and wealth. If Jupiter is beneficial then it can bestow you with all the riches. The native is likely to be blessed with offspring, wealth and wisdom. However, if Jupiter is malefic or weak then it can create problems in life. It can have the opposite effect and a person may be devoid of wealth, wisdom or offspring. A person can also get disrepute in society.

Jupiter takes 13 months to orbit one zodiac sign and 12 years to orbit the whole zodiac. The friendly planets of Jupiter are Sun, Moon, and Mars. The enemy planets are Mercury & Venus, and it's neutral towards Saturn & Rahu. The color associated with planet Jupiter is Yellow, and the precious stone is Yellow Sapphire. Ruler of Sagittarius and Pisces. Jupiter rules over Sagittarius and is co ruler of Pisces. With Sagittarius the optimism of Jupiter is translated often into a positive personality always searching over the horizon for an expansion in faith and knowledge and challenge. With Pisces, the spirituality of Jupiter leads to an understanding and sympathy for the different races and faiths on the planet. Once the inner planets have been understood and personalised, the individual can now deal with collective issues and not lose themselves in the process. For this reason, Jupiter is considered less of a personal planet than a planet to do with how we relate to the society we find ourselves in. It is however far closer than the three outer planets which are known as transpersonal planets and have an influence over whole generations.

Jupiter in the Signs:

Jupiter in Water Element Signs - provides expansion and nurturing relationships. Elevates knowledge through creativity and artistic imagination. Jupiter in Fire Element Signs - provides expansion and good luck in challenges, in leadership roles, in positions of responsibility. Stimulates the intellect. Jupiter in Earth Element Signs - provides expansion and encourages questioning of rules established. It favors the acquisition of material goods, intellectual production and a comfortable standard of living. Jupiter in Air Element Signs - provides expansion and encourages learning, the taste for novelty, healthy social relationships and a feeling of satisfaction in helping others.

Jupiter in Aries:

Believes in the power of positivity, that life is what you make of it. Loves competition, doing things independently. Values instant results. Attracts the most good fortune when he/she takes the lead, initiates, inspires, and demonstrates enthusiasm and courage.

Jupiter in Taurus:

Delights in sensual pleasures and wants the good life. A strong feeling of what they are worth attracts success. Good instincts for finances, what things are worth/good products, and investing. Attracts the most “good fortune” when they are charitable, generous but discriminating, and patient. They should watch for over-indulgence.

Jupiter in Gemini:

Attracts the most good fortune when they use their wit and ingeniousness, are versatile, sociable, curious, and put others at ease with friendliness and sincere curiosity. Values the intellect and sees opportunities to grow and succeed through intellectual, verbal, and written channels. Believes that intelligence and knowledge are the keys to solving problems.

Jupiter in Cancer:

Attracts the most good fortune when they are sympathetic and charitable. Uses their powers to save and accumulate, and comforts others. Real estate and the food industry can be prosperous avenues. Values tradition and works towards security. Relies mostly on gut instincts when it comes to pursuing goals and business success.

Jupiter in Leo:

Attracts the most good fortune when they express magnanimity, are generous with others, inspire confidence in those around them, conduct themselves with dignity and sincerity, and avoid the pitfall of excessive egotism. Prosperous areas are creative ones, entertainment, children, and recreation. They take pride in everything they do. Generosity brings success.

Jupiter in Virgo:

Attracts the most good fortune when they are helpful, honest, orderly, and when they pay attention to details. The service industries, nutrition, and health are prosperous avenues. Practical and technical knowledge and skills are most valued. A real problem solver and others appreciate their help. Doesn't always feel lucky or especially ambitious. Instead, hard work is valued.

Jupiter in Libra:

Attracts the most good fortune when they are fair-minded, treat others with equality, are bending and compromising without being a “doormat”, are gracious, and use their talents at promoting and mediating. They value people and relationships, and might succeed best in partnership. Relating as equals is important to them. The arts, architecture, law, math, mediating, and politics are possible avenues for success. Use of charm and grace to reach goals.

Jupiter in Scorpio:

Attracts the most good fortune when they put their “all” into a project or undertaking, and use their magnetic powers to heal others. Enthusiastic for deeper studies and meanings, all that is taboo or mysterious, psychology. Values decisiveness, intensity, willpower, commitment, and strength. Very strong problem solver who cuts to the chase. Science and research may be prosperous avenues.

Jupiter in Sagittarius:

Attracts the most good fortune when they are open-handed and generous, tolerant, and practice what they preach. Can be inspirational, and find success in travel, education, teaching, sports, publishing, and foreign cultures. Very philosophical, forward-looking, and enthusiastic. Has strong morals. Strongly values freedom of movement and expression.

Jupiter in Capricorn:

Attracts the most good fortune when they organize and direct, conduct themselves with integrity, are ethical and mature. Values the long term, achievement, responsibility, and manifestation. Succeeds through resourcefulness and avoiding activities that waste time, energy, or resources. Good at streamlining. Position or status is important to them.

Jupiter in Aquarius:

Attracts the most good fortune when they are tolerant and fair, inventive, impartial, and cooperative. Values people and personal freedom most. Wants to show a unique perspective or original and unique skills and talents. Open to new methods and progress. Great tolerance and humanitarianism.

Jupiter in Pisces:

Attracts the most good fortune when they are charitable, tender, devoted, compassionate, looking out for the underdog, and giving generously. Values compassion and charity, and is motivated by a universal vision. Peaceful personal philosophy. Faith in the goodness of life brings rewards.

Jupiter Transition in 12 Houses:

Jupiter transitions in different houses will have different impacts. As per the birth chart, Jupiter in the first house represents health and the immune system, while in the second house it grants wealth. Jupiter in the fifth house is responsible for knowledge, wisdom and children. Jupiter in the ninth house gives recognition to the government and authority. Jupiter is the most evident or pratyaksha God in the horoscope. Jupiter is called

the Jeeva or soul of a person in Astrology. Jupiter relates with soul searching or aatm- manthan of a native, which makes it the most important planet of the horoscope

Jupiter in 1st House in Ascendant in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 1st house gives immense success, wealth and prosperity in life after the age of 45. Guru in 1st house gives meritorious and prosperous children in life. Native may attain popularity and success in career after the age of 40. Native's fortune and prosperity will rise after marriage. Jupiter here in lagna protects native from any kind of bad situation in life. Person with Jupiter in their 1st house will have almighty blessing from very young age and native's inclination towards spirituality will increase from young age.

Jupiter in 2nd House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 2nd house will make native liberal and charitable. Jupiter in 2nd house will bestow native much wealth through their business and occupation. Person with Jupiter in 2nd house might get born in aristocratic family or wealthy family. Native will be foodie and will lead a very luxurious life after the age of 34. Native may prefer arranged marriage over love marriage in young age. Jupiter in 2nd house gives native talent in singing or music. Native can have some weight problem in later stages in life. Native will be fond of fast food which may lead to ill health in middle years of life.

Jupiter in 3rd House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 3rd house gives struggle in life till 30 years of age. Native might achieve fame and success in glamour or cine world after the age of 21 but native will face some tension and several issues in life till 30 years of age. Person might face some false allegation in life. Jupiter in 3rd house will give person lot of abundance and family support all through life. Native will have obedient and popular children. Jupiter in this house gives success and wealth through creativity or artistic talent. Native may also become a popular writer or journalist. Career in Marketing and advertising field will lead to very wealthy and happy life. There will be much support from siblings in native's life.

Jupiter in 4th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 4th house in Kundli gives lavish lifestyle and expansion of wealth and fortune from the age of 40. Although, native will have high expenses and health trouble in life. Person may suffer from heart trouble or nerve problem in life. Native may also face blood pressure problem or diabetic problem in life. Jupiter in 4th house gives abundance expansion of properties in life. Native may possess multiple vehicle and multiple houses in life from the age of 38. Native might not save much liquid wealth in life.

Jupiter in 5th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 5th house gives native success in life after the birth of their children. Native's progeny may become very successful and very popular in life. Native will become much wealthy after 35 years of age. Jupiter in 5th house gives artistic and literary taste in life. Native will be highly educated and he or she may become a popular writer, actor, painter, sports star, novelist in life. Jupiter in 5th house gives lot of financial abundance and savings from the age of 38. Native will have fulfilling romantic life.

Jupiter in 6th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 6th house gives struggle and hindrance in career and service life. Native will face financial problem during young age and their career will not be stable till 39 years of age. Native will face dejection and failure in love affair. Person might also face defamation due to court case or through litigation. Native will get full father support in life especially in finances. Person will see growth in life only after hardship, struggle and persistent effort in their field of work. Native can become a successful doctor or may acquire government job in life.

Jupiter in 7th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 7th house gives luck, good fortune and transformation in life after marriage. Native will struggle in life till 28 years of age. Native may see great success in life in the field of business or in showbiz industry after 26 years of age. Person will prosper and become very happy after marriage if 7th lord is well placed and not under malefic influence. Native's spouse will bring luck, happiness, love, charm in life of native after marriage. All the failures of native will vanish and native will quickly rise to good position in life with good pace. Native's spouse will be very caring, devoted and supportive towards native. Marriage will bring positive change in life for the native.

Jupiter in 8th House in Natal Chart:

Person may get money or house through inheritance or through marriage. Native will become wealthy after marriage. Some native may remain unmarried all their life. Jupiter in 8th house will give success in the field of astrology, occult and spirituality. Jupiter in 8th house gives lot of troubles, health issues, and struggle till the age of 33. Jupiter in 8th makes native bereft of family support and support from authorities. Jupiter in 8th house gives failures and dejection in their love life. Native may wander aimlessly in life for few years.

Jupiter in 9th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 9th house gives fortune in foreign land. Person will get success through higher education in foreign land. Native may get settle in foreign land as well. Person may become a popular scholar or preacher in life. Jupiter in 9th house will give much wealth after marriage. Jupiter in 9th house also gives successful

children and happy peaceful life. Jupiter in 9th house will give full support from parents both financially and mentally.

Jupiter in 10th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 10th house gives success in government field. Native may become professor, teacher officer, diplomat, IAS, IPS, IFS in life. Person may also work in embassy in foreign land. Person will attain high position in life may get success in politics as well. Native will have high class business or government post with high income in life. Person may also earn multiple sources in life.

Jupiter in 11th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 11th house give all round success in life and prosperity after marriage. Native will have love marriage and may attain success from the age of 34. Native will get gains and profit in their occupation or business through their large network circle. Person may become a lawyer, barrister in life. Native may become a civil engineer or real estate businessman as well. Jupiter in 11th house gives multiple love affairs in life even after marriage. Sometimes clandestine affairs will land native in trouble through scandals.

Jupiter in 12th House in Natal Chart:

Jupiter in 12th house gives troublesome married life. Native's spouse might cheat him or her. Native will have health problems regarding liver, lungs and bones. Person will travel in foreign land and will achieve success in foreign place. Native will have high expenses in life but he or she will have large liquid money savings. Person will love travel business and adventure sports. Native will get success in their life after the age of 42. Native will get some bed pleasures outside relationship or marriage.

Yogas Made By Jupiter in Relation with Other Planets:

- The Mars and Jupiter combination makes the person energetic and active.
- The person with Jupiter and Venus combinations is a jackpot.
- The conjunction of Saturn with Jupiter makes the person highly successful.

Mahapurusha Hamsa Yoga:

When Jupiter, exalted (in Karka) or in its own sign (Dhanu or Meena), is located in a kendra. One born in Hamsa yoga has a fair complexion, prominent cheeks, beautiful face and a golden luster in his skin. His nails and palms are red, his feet are lovely and his eyes have the pallor of honey. His voice is sweet like that of a swan.

Ashtalakshmi Yoga:

If in a horoscope Guru is placed in Kendra (angular houses) or the 1st, 4th or 7th or 10th houses and Rahu is placed in 6th house. A person who is born with Ashtalakshmi yoga is blessed with Eightfold prosperity of Goddesses Ashta-Lakshmi i.e. Renowned and earned name, worldwide fame, Great prosperity, satisfied, peaceful, pleasure-full and enjoyment in their lifetime. The Eightfold Prosperity has been described by Vedic terminology as the Ashta Lakshmi, which are as below:

- The Original & Complete Prosperity (Adi Lakshmi or Mahalakshmi).
- Prosperity of Wealth (Dhana Lakshmi).
- Prosperity of food & bhoga (Dhanya Lakshmi).
- Prosperity of Royal status & Power (Gaja/Vaibhav Lakshmi).
- Prosperity of Children (Santana Lakshmi).
- Prosperity of Patience & Tolerance (Dhairya Lakshmi).
- Prosperity of success & victory (Vijaya Lakshmi).
- Prosperity of Education & Wisdom (Vidya Lakshmi).

Dhana Yoga:

The Jupiter occupying the 5th house identical with its own rashi (Dhanu/Meena), and Mercury in the 11th house. This yoga is Benefic in nature. This combination leads to excessive wealth.

Akand Samrajya Yoga:

This Yoga happens when Jupiter is the lord of 2nd or 5th house in strong position meaning it is exalted or in its own sign. And the lord of the 11th house should be in Kendra to Moon. If all of these positions are not afflicted by malefic planets then the person is blessed with a very long life and lots of good fortune throughout this lifetime.

Vasuman Yoga:

If in the birth chart, Jupiter, Mercury and Venus are placed in 3rd, 6th, 10th or 11th houses from ascendant or moon, Vasuman Yoga is formed. Depending upon the strength of this Yoga, the person shall have immense wealth in his lifetime. He will gain a lot of prosperity and fortune.

Adhi Yoga:

This Yoga is formed when the Jupiter, Venus and Mercury is placed in 6th, 7th or 9th house from lagna or Moon. This Yoga gives the native the ability to earn a lot of money in life. Such a native will accumulate a lot of wealth in their lifetime.

Gajakeshari Yoga:

Jupiter forms Gajakeshari yoga with the Moon. Gajakesari Yoga is known to be the most powerful and propitious yogas, known in Vedic astrology. This yoga is formed when a Kendra from the Moon is occupied by Jupiter. These are 1, 4, 7, 10th houses from the Moon. It is believed that it brings about sharp intellectual abilities and immense prosperity in one's life. The person with this yoga will be highly loved and respected by the people around him.

Chandra-Mangal-Buddh-Guru-Shani Yoga:

Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, and Saturn conjunct with each other to form the above yoga. This yoga is Malefic in nature. The horoscope will be Wicked, poor, living on begged food, and suffers night-blindness.

Mahapatka Yoga:

Moon cojoined with Rahu, aspected by Jupiter which is under malefic association..The person is a heinous sinner.

Kalanidhi Yoga:

Kalanidhi Yoga is formed in five different ways in any Birth Chart. There are five different rules and the presence of even one is sufficient for the formation of Kalanidhi Yoga.

Rule (1): In a Native's Birth Chart, if Movable sign i.e. Aries, Cancer, Libra or Capricorn arises in Birth Ascendent and Jupiter conjunct with Bhagyasha (Lord of the Ninth house). Apart of this Lord of 5th house is placed in the 5th house and strong Karmasha (Lord of 10th house) occupied 11th house of income/gain, then Kalanidhi Yoga is formed.

Rule (2): In a Native's Birth Chart, if Navamsha of Movable sign i.e. Aries, Cancer, Libra or Capricorn arises in Birth Ascendent and Jupiter conjunct with Bhagyasha (Lord of the Ninth house) in the Ascendent only. Apart of this Lord of 5th house is placed in the 5th house and strong Karmasha (Lord of 10th house) occupied 11th house of income/gain, then Kalanidhi Yoga is formed.

Rule (3): If Jupiter is conjunct with or aspected by Mercury and Venus both either in the 2nd or in the 5th or in the 9th house then Kalanidhi Yoga occurs.

Rule (4): If Jupiter occupies the 2nd or 5th house and in the signs of Mercury (i.e. Gemini/Virgo) or Venus (Taurus/Libra), Kalanidhi yoga occurs.

Rule (5): If Mercury & Venus conjoined and occupied in the 2nd or 5th house and the signs of Jupiter (i.e. Sagittarius/Pisces), Kalanidhi yoga occurs.

The native with Kalanidhi yoga will be extremely wealthy, Very healthy, learned, honoured and Powered by the king / government. The person blessed with this yoga is highly passionate, good-natured, noble, humble, Charitable, rewarded by kings (rulers), commands different kinds of conveyances and all sorts of royal comforts. A Native bestow with this yoga having all materialistic & worldly pleasures and enjoyments, wealth, property, popularity, fame, respect and success in their life. A Native bestow with this Yoga lives his life like a king and may be a very successful leaders/ businessman/Professionals in their work area.

Shakata Yoga:

This is when Jupiter is in the 6th, 8th, or 12th house from the Moon. Shakata means "cart", or wheel. The fortunes of this person will rise and fall. It means fluctuating fortunes. If there is either the Adhi or Vasumati Yogas, then the Shakata Yoga is cancelled.

Raja Yogas Caused by Planets in Conjunction with Jupiter:

Surya Guru Raja Yoga:

Surya-Guru Raja Yoga is one of the best formations in a horoscope which is achieved through a favourable combination of Surya (Sun) and Guru (Jupiter). Jupiter and Sun should either be joined together, aspect to each other or in opposite positions and the Jupiter should neither retrograde nor should it be too close to the Sun for the formation of Surya-Guru Raja Yoga.

Guru Chandra Yoga:

The combination, when Guru conjoins Chandra or aspects it from trikona houses, 5th and 9th, is termed as Guru Chandra yoga. Moon and Jupiter are natural friends in vedic astrology and thus when both combines in particular house then it enriches features of that particular house.

Guru Mangal Yoga:

Guru and Mars are conjuncted in one house then Guru Mangal yoga is formed. Guru Mangal yoga is formed when Mars is placed in the 1st house, and Jupiter is placed in the 7th house. This yoga will define your demeanour and enrich your personality. The fiery traits of Mars such as strength, aggression, energy, etc will dominate your personality along with the positive powers of Jupiter which will make you cheerful, spiritual, intelligent and inclined towards education.

Saraswati Yoga:

Saraswati Yoga is When Jupiter, Mercury and Venus are placed in a kendra(Ascendant, 4th house, 7th house, 10th house) or Trikona (5th and 9th house) or in Second House and Jupiter is strongly placed in own house or in a friendly sign or in a exaltion sign Saraswati Yoga is created in a Horoscope. The individual with

Saraswati Yoga will expertise in the skill of composing drama, prose, and poetry. He might also be an excellent Mathematician. The native with Saraswati Yoga shall possess all that Goddess Saraswati is known for.

Guru Sukra Yoga:

When Jupiter and Venus are placed in one house then guru shukra yoga forms in birth chart. In Vedic astrology Jupiter enemy is Venus while Venus does not have enmity with Jupiter. Jupiter is the Jeeva or Jeeva Karaka. Means it is the planet without which Human cannot survive. Similarly Venus or Sukra is the Owner of Sanjeevani with which a Dead person can become Alive.

Dharma Karmadhipati Yoga:

Jupiter and Saturn conjunction in one house or aspecting each other (opposite) forms Dharma karmadhipati yoga. The persons with this yoga are more inclined to religious activities, spiritualism and temple activities.

Guru Chandal Yoga:

Guru planet comes in conjunction with rahu in natal chart it is known as Guru Chandal Yoga. This yoga may be beneficial or malefic according to the jupiter and rahu's benefic and malefic nature. This makes a negative yoga in the birth chart where the individual is inclined towards immoral and unethical behaviour. This yoga will make a person become naturally rebellious which may be good for enemies but it makes the person rebel with their own guru, marriage and many other areas of life. It makes the person have a hard time giving respect to others and this can cause problems in career and in life.

Kela Yoga / Ganesha Yoga / Koteeswara Yoga:

This yoga is formed when jupiter and ketu get conjuncted. Unlike Rahu, Kethu does not grab the strength of the conjoining planet. Since Kethu is a planet symbolising total wisdom, its conjunction with Guru at certain circumstances gives rise to immense benefits. Especially in houses wherein Kethu is strong like Vrischik, Kanya or in moveable signs like Mesha or Kataka, this alignment would give excellent results during Guru and Kethu dasas (major periods). If this conjunction occurs in moveable signs then the native would move to other states or other countries towards gaining good financial prospects.

Conclusion:

Thus from this article we can come across various yogas caused by jupiter in person with single planet and multiple planet combinations and aspects. More the yogas in a horoscope make the person more blissful and wealthy.

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